

Detecting Differential Item Functioning in Testlets Through Bayesian Analyses

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Item Dependencies

- Occur when responses to items depend upon some commonality
 - Share the same stimuli
 - Cross-item cuing
- Item clusters controlled through secondary latent trait / dimension

Testlet Random Item Mixture Model

$$\begin{aligned}
 (Resp_{ijg} | C_j = 0) &\sim \text{Bernoulli}(\Phi(\alpha_{1j}\theta_{ig} - \beta_j + \alpha_{2j}\gamma_{d(j)i})) \\
 (Resp_{ijg} | C_j = 1) &\sim \text{Bernoulli}(\Phi(\alpha_{1j}\theta_{ig} - \beta_{jg} + \alpha_{2j}\gamma_{d(j)i})) \\
 \theta_{\mu 1} &= 0 \\
 \theta_{\mu 2} &\sim \text{Unif}(-3,3) \\
 \theta_{\sigma 1}, \theta_{\sigma 2} &= 1 \\
 \gamma_{d(j)i} &\sim \text{Norm}(0,1) \\
 \alpha_{1j}, \alpha_{2j} &\sim \text{Lnorm}(0, .5) \\
 (\beta_j | C_j = 0) &\sim \text{Norm}(0, \beta_1\sigma) \\
 (\beta_{j1}, \beta_{j2} | C_j = 1) &\sim \text{MVN}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1\sigma^2 & \rho\beta_1\sigma\beta_2\sigma \\ \rho\beta_1\sigma\beta_2\sigma & \beta_2\sigma^2 \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
 \rho &\sim \text{Unif}(-1,1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Testlet Model

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(y_{ij} = 1) &= \Phi(\alpha_{1j}\theta_i - t_j + \alpha_{2j}\gamma_{d(j)i}) \\
 \theta_i &\sim N(0,1) \\
 \gamma_{d(j)i} &\sim N(0,1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Simulation Study

Differential Item Functioning

- When equal-ability examinees have different item responding probabilities as a function of their group membership
- Measurement
 - Assessment: Prevents test fairness
 - Explanatory: Prevents valid inferences
- Purpose of this study is to compare different approaches of detecting DIF

Power: 0.8 α

Power: 1.6 α

Type I: 0.8 α

Type I: 1.6 α

Mixture vs P-value: 0.8 α

Mixture vs P-value: 1.6 α

